

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Valorisation of a lignin-rich residue via catalytic pyrolysis over ZrO₂/ZSM-5 technical catalyst

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FIGURES

Figure S1. Weight loss and DTG curves for raw the lignocellulose (A) and the lignin-rich residue (B). Blue: experimental weight loss curve; Red: experimental DTG curve; Green, light and dark blue curves: calculated by deconvolution of the experimental DTG curve using Origin software; and Black dash: Simulated DTG curves with Origin software.

Figure S2. XRD patterns (A) and Ar adsorption-desorption isotherms (B) for n-ZSM-5 and ZrO₂/n-ZSM-5-ATP catalysts.

TABLES

Table S1. Physicochemical properties of n-ZSM-5 and ZrO₂/n-ZSM-5-ATP catalysts [39].

Catalyst	Si/Al	ZrO ₂ ^a (wt%)	S _{BET} ^b (m ² /g)	S _{MIC} ^c (m ² /g)	S _{MES+EXT} ^d (m ² /g)	V _{MIC} ^e (cm ³ /g)	V _T ^f (cm ³ /g)	Acidity ^g (mmol/g)	Basicity ^h (μmol/g)
n-ZSM-5	42	-	445	312	133	0.186	0.512	0.28	3.26
ZrO ₂ /n-ZSM-5-ATP	42	10.5	325	223	102	0.133	0.445	0.38	18.39

^a Measured by ICP-OES, quantities expressed per amount of zeolite.

^b BET surface area. ^c Micropore surface area, calculated from NL-DFT. ^d Mesopore + external surface area. ^e Micropore volume. ^f Total pore volume at P/P₀ ≈ 0.98. ^g Measured by TPD-NH₃. ^h Measured by TPD-CO₂. Quantities expressed per amount of catalyst.

Table S2. Proximate and elemental analyses of the chars obtained by pyrolysis of the lignin-rich residue at different temperatures.

Experiment	Proximate analysis (wt% char, db)				HHV (MJ/kg _{char} , db)
	Volatile matter	Ash	Fixed carbon		
TP 500/450	27.4	10.1	62.5		
TP 550/450	23.3	11.5	65.2		
TP 600/450	19.8	12.4	67.8		
TP 650/450	18.8	13.1	68.1		
	Elemental analysis (wt% char, daf)				HHV (MJ/kg _{char} , db)
	C	H	N	O	
TP 500/450	80.6	3.4	2.4	13.6	27.4
TP 550/450	81.3	3.1	2.6	13.0	26.9
TP 600/450	85.0	2.6	2.4	10.0	27.5
TP 650/450	87.8	2.4	2.4	7.4	28.1

* db: dry basis

** daf: dry and ash-free basis